

Key Identifying and predicting social lifestyles in people's trajectories by neural networks

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1. Introduction

Thanks to the increasing use of GPS devices, wearable sensors, and location-based services, a significant amount of data on human movement has been collected. This data can be used for analyzing the mobility patterns of people, their behaviour, and lifestyles.

Aim

To create a machine learning pipeline that identifies a person's lifestyles according to daily trajectories in his movements, which we refer to as mobility patterns, and predicts a his lifestyles.

2. Material and methods

To create a machine learning pipeline that identifies a person's lifestyles according to daily trajectories in his movements, which we refer to as mobility patterns, and predicts a his lifestyles.

3. Results

The results and adding some background knowledge we have about most of the 38 users, we can conclude that when the mobility patterns of a user have a low level of "uncertainty," e.g., his routine is stable, the CLSTM model has a high level of accuracy. We identify three groups of users according to the variability/uncertainty in their mobility patterns. Those with stationary mobility patterns; those with changing mobility patterns, but still some stationarity; and those with mobility patterns that change very frequently.

4. Conclusions

Our system shows accuracy and generalizability in lifestyle identification and prediction (both for a novel trajectory and a novel user) that are superior to those shown by state-of-the-art algorithms.

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5. Keywords

Convolutional neural network; Embedding; Human behaviour; Lifestyle; Long short-term memory; Mobility patterns; Place of interest; Recurrent neural network; Sequence classification; Word2vec

Author biography

Eyal Ben Zion received his Ph.D. from the Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) Department at Ben-Gurion University of the Negev in February 2018. In his dissertation, he studied machine learning methods to analyze, learn, identify, and predict human mobility patterns from data. He holds a BSc and an MSc also from the IEM Department at Ben-Gurion University. Today, Eyal works for Cerebri AI as a data scientist.